

**IS'HOQXON IBRAT NOMIDAGI
NAMANGAN DAVLAT CHET TILLARI
INSTITUTI**

**«BADIY VA ILMIY
TARJIMANING
LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK
MUAMMOLARI VA
ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDA
KOMPARATIVISTIK
YONDASHUVLAR»**

**XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY
ANJUMAN**

**2024-YIL
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MUAMMOLARI VA ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKDA KOMPARATIVISTIK
YONDASHUVLAR”**

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Собранные и исследованные понятия представляют собой готовый материал для более полного двуязычного терминологического толкового словаря научно-педагогических терминов.

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SPECIAL CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF GOTHIC NOVELS

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Abstract: This thesis aims to reveal the specific features of Gothic novels that distinguish them from other types of novels with relevant examples, which we will consider in the examples of characters, time, places, atmosphere and supernatural situations.

Key words: Gothic literature, ghosts, mystery, gothic tale, haunted house, castle ruins, paranormal, spiritual, damsel.

Gothic literature originally arose in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, primarily in England, shortly in the US as well. It tells intriguing, thrilling, and supernatural stories. Because of its Romanticism roots, it still has romantic overtones despite its horror and terror elements. It aims to go deeper and deeper

into the subject than the Romantic works of the time. When Gothic literature first appeared, its writers accepted the idea that the setting would always be a ruined castle, an abandoned peak, or some barren area. Instead of only describing the dread, they use ambiance. This is precisely how elements of Gothic literature differ from traditional horror literature. The plot would often feature hidden secrets, ghosts, vampires, and miserable existence, with a constant aura of mysticism, fear, and intense feelings. Today, the Gothic continues to influence the novel, the short story, and poetry, and provides a major source of themes and elements in film making.

Gothic writers use both the story and its underlying meaning, or theme, to express their point. Also, the darkest aspects of humanity are highlighted by gothic themes. The following are some of the prominent themes of Gothicism:

- Appearance vs Reality
- Doppelganger/Duality of humanity
- Isolation and seclusion
- Challenging gender roles
- Imbalance of power
- Corruption of innocence
- Place
- Romance
- Injustice
- Searching for the truth

The Gothic is a genre that continually looks at unexplainable happenings and stimulates encounters with the extraordinary. It is characterized by spiritual uneasiness. Gothic literature terrifies by exposing readers to the evils that exist in our society. **Furthermore, the key elements of Gothic literature have distinct features that set the tone for this dark and mysterious genre. Key elements of gothic literature:**

Characters

Gothic fiction characters often find themselves in strange settings when they depart from the secure world they were familiar with. In this genre, ghosts are perfectly suited to explore patterns of isolation and captivity, and superstitions, omens, and curses increase the sense of mystery.

Place

A place is arguably the most significant aspect of the gothic tale. The majority will immediately create images of moors and heaths, of lonely, foreboding places, and of castles and gloomy homes. A haunted home or building appears in many Gothic novels. However, in practice, the house represents more than simply physical structures. It is a reflection of the mind, dividing and securing life's realities before lies and dishonesty return to haunt our characters. Moreover, the action takes place in and around an old castle or an old mansion, or the ruins of an old castle. Sometimes the edifice is seemingly abandoned, sometimes occupied, and sometimes it's not clear whether the building has occupants (human or

otherwise). The castle often contains secret passages, trap doors, secret rooms, trick panels with hidden levers, dark or hidden staircases, and possibly ruined sections. The castle may be near, on top of, or connected to caves, which lend their own haunting flavour with their darkness, uneven floors, branchings, claustrophobia, echoes of unusual sounds, and mystery. And in horror-Gothic, caves are often home to terrifying creatures such as monsters, or deviant forms of humans: vampires, zombies, werewolf or old witches.

Atmosphere

Gothic literature is filled with atmosphere. Although the place has a significant influence on the atmosphere, it goes far beyond that. A writer can create an atmosphere with their tone and language choices, with suggested meanings, internal and external conflicts, character development, and the creation of suspense and mystery. Furthermore, the atmosphere produced can often be restricted. There are limited opportunities for escape in these tiny settings.

The supernatural

If there aren't any ghosts in it, can we still call gothic fiction gothic? Sometimes, everything is just in the mind, but that's where gothic literature excels beyond all other genres: it allows you to use your imagination to create the story. Sometimes, what may be there is far more terrifying than what is. But the best part about Gothic fiction is that it immerses us in a world of doubt, especially when it comes to the paranormal and spiritual.

Damsels

A damsel in distress tends to be a prominent character in classic gothic novels. It contributes to the subject of power imbalances in the genre where women were perceived as weaker and more often the targets of violent crimes. On the other hand, women are often portrayed as possessed, supernatural figures, although being associated with motherhood.

Time

Gothic fiction has a heavy focus on time. There is a concentration on promoting the past. It is common for aspects of the past to collide with the present, bringing danger, fear, and reality with them. But the characters' past doesn't just come catching up with them. There will always be something unsettlingly unfamiliar to go along with the past. The present is genuinely disturbed by the past.

Mystery and fear

One of the essential features of a great Gothic story is its ability to evoke feelings of the unknown and fear. Anything beyond scientific explanation opens the door to the unknowable, and the Gothic atmosphere only adds to the sense of mystery. Many Gothic stories include elements such as funerals, flickering candle flames, sinister potions, and other frightening details. For example, Anne Radcliffe's *The Mysteries of Udolpho* (1794) centers on Emily St. Aubert, an orphan girl who is an unwilling prisoner in the secluded chambers of a castle.

The Gothic novel is called the progenitor of modern literary trends: mysticism, horror and dark fantasy, yet it has its own specifics. In order to be

considered as gothic novel, it has to contain the characteristic features of the genre.

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MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTNING PAYDO BO‘LISHI VA RIVOSHLANISHI TARIXIGA NAZAR

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Annotatsion: This article discusses some issues of the history of intercultural communication, its origins, problems and development. The role of intercultural communication in the field of general culture and research into the opinions of scientists is presented.

Key words: Intercultural communication, social and cultural influence, interdependence of cultures, globalization.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo muloqot, va uning paydo bo‘lishi, muammolari hamda rivojlanish tarixidagi ayrim masalalar haqida gap yuritiladi. Madaniyatlararo muloqotning umummadaniyat sohasidagi o‘rni va olimlarning fikrlari yuzasidan izlanishlari keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Madaniyatlararo muloqot, ijtimoyi va madaniy ta’sir, madaniyatlarning o‘zaro bog‘liqligi, globallashuv.

Madaniyatlararo muloqot muammolari umummadaniyat sohasida globallashuvdan keng bo‘lib, madaniyatshunoslarni 1990-yillar boshidan boshlab o‘ziga jalb qila boshladi. Ushbu davrlardan boshlab etnik madaniy qadriyatlar, jahon madaniy makoni, madaniyatlarning o‘zaro bog‘likligi shakllari, usullari va natijalari, madaniy transformatsiyalar rivojlanishi yunalishlari birinchi bor alohida masalalar sifatida qo‘yila boshlandi.

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